

DEVELOPING DIGITAL TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The digital tourism industry offers various opportunities for both growth and development. This article explores different applications that are used worldwide in order to share the information, experience, and emotions between travelers. It also shows websites that tourists visit for booking hotels and buying tour packages. However, it also encounters some challenges that perhaps can prevent it from continuous innovations. These issues, include firstly the digital divide, where people, especially the older generation are not able or lack of knowledge about how to use gadgets throughout their lives to book a trip they want and travel around the world. This division creates inequality and a generation gap between youngsters and adolescents, limiting the ability to plan and make decisions. The other problem of the digitalization process is cyber security, and to be more precise, its scarcity in many fields, where tourism is not an exception. People can be easily attacked by intruders, and these kinds of criminals may have access to users' personal information and private conversations in applications and websites. The article will also introduce the solutions for those challenges.*

Key words: *Travel, tour, trip, digital tourism, tourism, social media, marketing, development, opportunities, tourist, traveler, experience, gadget, applications, booking, chatbot.*

Аннотация. *Индустрия цифрового туризма предлагает различные возможности для роста и развития. В этой статье рассматриваются различные приложения, которые используются по всему миру для обмена информацией, опытом и эмоциями между туристами. Также здесь представлены веб-сайты, которые они посещают для бронирования отелей и покупки туристических пакетов. Однако эта сфера деятельности сталкивается и с некоторыми препятствиями, которые могут мешать её непрерывным инновациям. Одна из таких проблем — цифровой разрыв, когда люди, особенно представители старшего поколения, не имеют навыков или знаний о том, как использовать гаджеты для бронирования поездок и путешествий по миру. Этот разрыв создаёт неравенство и поколенческий разрыв между молодёжью и подростками, ограничивая их возможности в планировании и принятии решений. Другая проблема цифровизации — кибербезопасность, а точнее её нехватка во многих сферах, включая туризм. Пользователи могут стать жертвами хакеров, которые получают доступ к их личной информации и частной переписке в приложениях и на сайтах. В статье также будут представлены возможные решения этих проблем.*

Ключевые слова: *Путешествие, тур, поездка, цифровой туризм, туризм, социальные сети, маркетинг, развитие, возможности, турист, путешественник, опыт, гаджет, приложения, бронирование, чат-бот.*

Annotatsiya. *Raqamli turizm sohasi o'sish va rivojlanish uchun ko'plab imkoniyatlar taqdim etadi. Ushbu maqolada sayohatchilar o'rtasida ma'lumot, tajriba va his-tuyg'ularni*

almashish uchun butun dunyoda qo'llaniladigan turli xil ilovalar o'rganiladi. Shuningdek, sayyohlar mehmonxonalarni bron qilish va tur paketlarini xarid qilish uchun tashrif buyuradigan veb-saytlar ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Biroq, bu soha doimiy innovatsiyalarga to'sqinlik qilishi mumkin bo'lgan ayrim qiyinchiliklarga ham duch kelmoqda. Bu muammolar, avvalo, raqamli tafovutni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu yerda odamlar, ayniqsa keksa avlod vakillari, o'zlari xohlagan sayohatni bron qilish va dunyo bo'ylab sayohat qilish uchun gadgetlardan qanday foydalanish to'g'risida yetarli bilim va ko'nikmalarga ega emaslar. Bu bo'linish yoshlar va katta yoshlilar o'rtasida tengsizlik va avlodlararo tafovutni keltirib chiqaradi, rejalashtirish va qaror qabul qilish imkoniyatlarini cheklaydi. Raqamlashtirish jarayonining yana bir muammosi - bu kibexavfsizlik, aniqrog'i, turizm ham bundan mustasno bo'lmagan ko'plab sohalarda uning yetarli darajada ta'minlanmaganligi.

***Kalit so'zlar:** Sayohat, tur, safar, raqamli turizm, turizm, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, marketing, rivojlanish, imkoniyatlar, sayohatchi, sayohatchi, tajriba, gadget, dasturlar, bron qilish, chatbot.*

Introduction. The Republic of Uzbekistan is considered to be a landlocked country in the middle of Central Asia. It is also a crucial member and player in the globalization of the tourism industry worldwide. The tourism and traveling sector has been estimated as a significant field for economic, financial, historical, and cultural growth for Uzbekistan, which has penetrated various regulations, reforms, and initiatives to improve its current situation in tourism and sustainability. At the present stage, one of the trends in the development of the world tourism industry is the development of Internet technologies, in other words, the modern development of tourism is taking place in the digital economy. That is, the digitization process has not bypassed the tourism industry, as in many other areas. (Khurramov O., 2020). These days, social media apps like Instagram, YouTube, and TikTok play an essential role in the tourism industry, because travelers are used to sharing their experience of the trip. On the other hand, companies and associations tend to use them as a marketing tool, to give pieces of advice on where to go, where to eat, and what kind of activities to do. Looking up and putting reviews of travel tours, hotels, and food has become an indispensable part of digital tourism development beside the online bookings. Digital travel, or digital tourism, refers to the travelers' use of digital tools throughout their experience. For example, booking travel products online may be thought about as a part of this method. (Azimov U. et al., 2022).

The implementation of online platforms, booking systems, and digital services, such as online ticketing, travel apps, and virtual tours, plays a significant role in the overall economy and development throughout Uzbekistan by not only enhancing the tourism experience but also creating broader economic and infrastructural benefits. These digital tools serve as vital instruments for modernizing the tourism industry, increasing global accessibility, and fostering greater economic integration across different sectors. The development of digital tourism in Uzbekistan has had a significant impact on the overall economy and people's experience by driving economic growth, creating innovation in tourism-related services, and transforming how both locals and visitors engage with the nation's rich cultural heritage. As digital technologies continue to evolve, they not only make tourism more accessible but also contribute to the broader modernization of Uzbekistan's infrastructure, promoting global competitiveness and local entrepreneurship. This digital transformation has also created new fields for businesses, enhanced

the quality of services provided, and satisfied travelers by offering greater convenience, personalized experiences, and real-time information, thereby playing a central role in the country's development. Despite all strengths, opportunities, and prospects, digitalization of the tourism industry and the experience it provides may sometimes face various challenges and threats, such as the digital divide, especially in rural areas or for older generations who may lack the skills to use gadgets; and protection of users' data. How these obstacles can affect the fields they are connected with and how to solve them will be discussed in this article.

Methods. As a result of observations and investigations of sites of tourism industries, hotels, and touristic centers we came across that, some hotels, that is to say, Savitskiy plaza Minyoun Hotel groups in Silk Road Samarkand, have organized Chatbots on their web sites. Nowadays, one of the most noticeable trends in the sphere of the tourism industry is the enhancement of Internet technologies. The continuous usage of the web, applications, and site resources by the vast majority of tourists has led to the emergence of the digital tourism sector, the development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to find and filter relevant recommendations for tourists to help them not get lost in their non-native atmosphere, as to be the country, city, region, or detached areas. First and foremost, digital tourism is considered to be the advancement of the tourism industry itself through various information technologies and telecommunication systems (TVs, radios, etc.). Digital tourism is a bunch of services provided to tourists or travelers before, during, and after their trip, travel, or journey.

One more aspect which we regard important to investigate in developing tourism is e-word of mouth and we included in our work for investigation. E-word of mouth can be good solution to promote the touristic centers. It should be admitted that chat bots can be expensive for medium touristic businesses but they can organize e-word of mouth.

Results. These days, there is a fashion for replacing traditional tourism with its digital version, and this is estimated to be mainly beneficial, as it saves people's time, money, and nerves. Tourism digitalization is now making the whole tourism business more adaptable and ready for changes in this continuously competing “digital world”. The hospitality, say, not only provides convenience to country visitors, but also helps to maintain conditions that benefit the tourist companies to earn more money and gain reviews. Digital tourism is nowadays a brand new feature and has already been widely used by humanity. They view recommendations and reviews from different websites like TripAdvisor, Orbitz, and Expedia. These allow people to differentiate the prices for tour packages and other services, as well as some other sites like Triplt, Ski, Google Flights, Priceline.com, Booking.com, Hotels.com, etc. The other bunch of applications, for instance Instagram, Facebook, OK, Picasa, iPhoto, and Flickr men and women use for posting photos and videos from their journeys. These apps have their own recommendations and provide the ability for users to follow other people and create content. Consequently, every mentioned modern technology that is used for different touristic purposes is based on digitalization of the tourism industry.

During the past two decades, digital tourism has widely spread across almost the whole world and gained popularity among people very quickly. The current and future development of the Uzbekistan tourism industry itself represents a unique chance for business boost and exchange of culture, showing the country's rich heritage and economic potential. This paragraph explores

the key factors of tourism development in our country, such as the initiation of government, improvements in infrastructure, and the promotion of cultural heritage.

In 2022, Uzbekistan welcomed approximately 2.5 million international tourists, marking a substantial recovery from the pandemic-induced decline in travel. This figure represented an increase of 30% compared to 2021, reflecting growing interest in the region's historical sites such as Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva. The government has set ambitious targets for tourism growth, aiming to attract 7 million tourists by 2024. To achieve this goal, several strategies have been put into place. (Otaboyev U., 2022)

Additionally, the independent investigators discuss the introduction of e-visa systems which have simplified travel procedures for many nationalities. As a result, visa issuance increased by 40% from 2022 to 2023. (Otaboyev U., 2022, as cited in Patterson I., & Tureav H., 2020)

According to the world's global statistics, tourism is the most profitable area in which a country can receive much financial potential. Over the past 10 years, it is crucial to notice that the most money-earning field in the tourism sector for Uzbekistan has been domestic tourism. As a research by the Minister of Tourism and Sports Mr. A. Abdukhakimov shows, the overall number of non-native citizens visiting our country was 1.5 million in 2020. For our country, it is not a small number yet this investigation was held during the world pandemic time. According to this research as well, the doubling of online booking trips to Uzbekistan is estimated.

Discussion and recommendation. The digital tourism industry has created various opportunities and chances for growth and development. Nevertheless, the problems it sometimes faces, particularly the digital divide, show the barriers that need addressing. Among older generations, particularly those who live in rural areas, the lack of digital technologies, such as smartphones, laptops, and the Internet, severely limits their ability to use all the services digital tourism provides. This situation forms inequality, because these groups do not have any benefit from online booking and traveling, rather than other age segments. Moreover, another disadvantage of using solely digital technologies may cause the leak of information, as IT security is considered to be a major problem in applications, websites, and any sites that contain users' personal and sensitive information. To solve these issues, authorities and private enterprises need to invest in digital programs, especially in rural areas and for the older population, to confidently say that no one is left behind in this process. In addition, the cyber security system, including the safety of personal accounts and data, should be continuously developed and implemented in people's digital lives. To summarize, with these strategies, the tourism industry can be successfully organized with digitalization, where every person can utilize it and can be secured from intruders.

One of the most effective ways of how people can use the benefits of online tourism is operating with chatbots which is also easy to use for all age groups. “A chatbot is a computer program able to entertain a natural language-based conversation with a human. . In the tourism sector, the first interactions delegated to a chatbot were used to support the search for tips and information (e.g., opening hours) of local restaurants and customer-care basic support”. (Calvaresi, D., et al., 2021). Chatbot is a tool that can help people with not only booking, but also searching for the most suitable and optimal choice to visit. Usually they are provided with the Artificial intelligence (AI). They simulate the human-like conversation and give customer support in a friendly and cheerful way. All the person needs to do is typing the information they are eager to find, and the robot suggests relevant answers and solutions. AI-powered chatbots are available in

the messengers like Telegram and Viber and in the social medias as Instagram and Facebook. The main advantage is that these kinds of bots work day and night, therefore it is not necessary to wait till the certain period of time. In order to promote both digital and sustainable tourism, the developing of chatbots with feedback and support is crucial in our daily life and can seriously impact the society and the country’s overall economic system.

The next recommendation on expanding touristic flow is inviting famous people, sportsmen and sportswomen and movie stars, tourism bloggers, and posts their opinions for promoting tourism potential of the country. (Sharipova U, 2023). It is real fact that people always impulse by others experience. If the experience is influential and impressive they also try to visit these places. E-word of mouth is important to regard in this case.

Conclusion. As we know, tourism is important part of our economy we should take into consideration recent changes in the sphere. Exchanging experience with other countries, using recent developments of the technologies will assist us to flourish tourism sector.

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